

1- Overview

OEEQ:

Product filter

All

Date filter

05/01/2023 31/03/2023

Recipe filter

IN OUT

Production filter

defect no-defect

Production

defect no-defect

Production WITH defects

IN OUT

Production WITHOUT defects

IN OUT

Production analysis:

Production over time

defect no-defect

Production WITH defects over time

IN OUT

Production by day of week

defect no-defect

Production by turn

defect no-defect

TOP Products produced

defect no-defect

TOP Defects

IN OUT

2- Detailed analysis of a defect

Defect filter

Broken paper (paper stations) ▾

Date filter

05/01/2023 📅 31/03/2023 📅

Recipe filter

IN OUT

Defect Recipe

● IN ● OUT

Products where this defect appears

● IN ● OUT

Process parameter values when this defect occurs:

Pressure

Thermal cycle

Top temperature

Paper RC

Paper VC

